

PRINSTON SMART ENGINEERS

Certificate of Internship HVAC DESIGN

Mohammad Shahil

Srinivas University

1SU19ME703

Intern Has Successfully Completed The Internship.
Intern Was Found To Be Good And Disciplined.
April 15th to May 15th, 2022.

PSEHVAC2903

www.prinstonSMART.com

Empowering and Inspiring
future professionals

Course4Job.com

PRINSTON SMART ENGINEERS

Certificate of Internship HVAC DESIGN

HUDAIF

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY MUKKA

1SU18ME007

Intern Has Successfully Completed The Internship.
Intern Was Found To Be Good And Disciplined.
March 1st to April 5th, 2022.

PSEHVAC2876

www.prinstonsmart.com

Course4job.com
Empowering and Inspiring
future professionals

Certificate Code: PSEHVAC2911

Prinston Smart Engineers
Engineering, Maintenance & Training Services

Internship Certificate

This Certificate is proudly presented to

Mohammed Sumaan

For successful completion of internship in

"HVAC DESIGN" with Grade "A" From April 15th to May 15th, 2022.

Usn : 1SU18ME018

Engineering, **College: Srinivas University** Services

UDYAM - DL-08-0031663

Authorized Signatory

PRINSTON SMART ENGINEERS

Certificate of Internship HVAC DESIGN

SANDESH S NAIK

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY ,MUKKA

1SU18ME027

**Intern Has Successfully Completed The Internship.
Intern Was Found To Be Good And Disciplined.**

March 1st to April 5th,2022.

PSEHVAC2878

www.prinstonsmart.com

Course4job.com

Empowering and Inspiring
future professionals

ELIXIRPRO ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS PVT. LTD.

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that Mr. Mohammad Safwan from Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology has successfully completed his internship at ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd. from 21/03/2022 to 23/05/2022.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various QC Inspection related activities.

We found him extremely inquisitive and hard working. He was very much interested to learn the functions of our core division and also willing to put his best efforts and get in to the depth of the subject to understand it better.

His association with us was very fruitful and we wish him all the best in his future endeavors.

Sincerely,

Nizamuddin Zafar

CIN : U74999TG2016PTC113168

Registered Office: 10-1-19/3/A 2nd Floor Masab Tank, Beside Golkonda Hotel Hyderabad 500028, India.

Email: info@elixirproengg.com, Phone no: +91 9381257763, 9676686102

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that **Mr. Raziq Shaheen** from **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology** has successfully completed his internship at **ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** from **21/03/2022** to **23/05/2022**.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various **QC Inspection** related activities.

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Sincerely,

Nizamuddin Zafar

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Registered Office: 10-1-19/3/A 2nd Floor Masab Tank, Beside Golkonda Hotel Hyderabad, 500028, India,

Email: info@elixirproengg.com, Phone no +91 9381257763, 9676686102

Date: 26/05/22

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Sincerely,

Nizamuddin Zafar

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Email: info@elixirproengg.com, Phone no +91 9381257763, 9676686102

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that **Mr. Mohammed Shahir** from **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology** has successfully completed his internship at **ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** from **21/03/2022** to **23/05/2022**.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various **QC Inspection** related activities.

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Sincerely,

Nizamuddin Zafar

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Email: info@elixirproengg.com, Phone no +91 9381257763, 9676686102

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that **Mr. Sheik Mohammed Shefan** from **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology** has successfully completed his internship at **ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** from **21/03/2022** to **23/05/2022**.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various **QC Inspection** related activities.

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Sincerely,

Nizamuddin Zafar

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Email:info@elixirproengg.com, Phone no+91 9381257763,9676686102

यांत्रिकी अभियान्त्रिक विभाग
DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
राष्ट्रीय प्रौद्योगिकी संस्थान कर्नाटक, सुरत्कल
NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KARNATAKA, SURATHKAL

Date: 28.03.2022

INTERNSHIP CERTIFICATE

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mrs. VAISHNAVI VIJAY RAWAL student of Institute of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru. .M.TECH Thermal Power Engineering successfully completed her Third semester internship in the field of Solar Energy from 01/11/2021 to 28/02/2022(16 weeks) under the guidance of Dr.N.Gnanasekaran, Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Karnataka .

We wish her all the best in future endeavors.

(Dr. N. GNANASEKARAN)

Address: P.O. Srinivasnagar, Mangalore - 575 025, Karnataka State, India

Phone: 0824-2473049, 0824-2474058, email: hodmechanical@nitk.ac.in Fax: 0824-2474033/4039, web: www.nitk.ac.in

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that Mr. Mohammed Thabsheer from Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology has successfully completed his internship at ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd. from 21/03/2022 to 23/05/2022.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various QC Inspection related activities.

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ELIXIRPRO ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS PVT. LTD.

(MSME & ISO-9001:2015 CERTIFIED COMPANY)

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that Mr. Mohammed Ejaz from Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology has successfully completed his internship at ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd. from 21/03/2022 to 23/05/2022.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various QC Inspection related activities.

We found him extremely inquisitive and hard working. He was very much interested to learn the functions of our core division and also willing to put his best efforts and get in to the depth of the subject to understand it better.

His association with us was very fruitful and we wish him all the best in his future endeavors.

Sincerely,

Nizamuddin Zafar

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that **Mr. Sohail Moidin** from **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology** has successfully completed his internship at **ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** from **21/03/2022** to **23/05/2022**.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various **QC Inspection** related activities.

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Email: info@elixirproengg.com, Phone no +91 9381257763, 9676686102

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that **Mr. Nameer Hussain** from **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology** has successfully completed his internship at **ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** from **21/03/2022** to **23/05/2022**.

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Sincerely,

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Email: info@elixirproengg.com, Phone no +91 9381257763, 9676686102

lms.decibelslab.com

Issued: 2022-04-19

Certificate ID: vbtgl1a2fj

This is to certify

Sheldon Alva

has undergone the internship in Decibels Lab Pvt Ltd, for the duration of 4 weeks from 14th March to 09th April 2022

INTERNSHIP
PARTICIPATION
CERTIFICATE

Suraj S D,
Co-founder & CEO
Decibels Lab Pvt Ltd

During the tenure intern was involved in,
Mathematical Modeling of Mechanical Systems.

Decibels Lab Private Limited
#2362, 24th main road
1st sector, HSR layout
Bangalore, Karnataka, 560102
CIN:U80904KA2019PTC126675

Project completed during the internship are Model-Based Design of NiMh Cell, Spring Mass Damper & Thermal modeling of house.

Date: 26/05/22

Sub: Internship Completion Letter

We are glad to inform you that **Mr. Mohammed Ismail** from **Srinivas University Institute of Engineering & Technology** has successfully completed his internship at **ElixirPro Engineering Solutions Pvt. Ltd.** from **21/03/2022** to **23/05/2022**.

During his internship, he was exposed to the various **QC Inspection** related activities.

We found him extremely inquisitive and hard working, He was very much interested to learn the functions of our core division and also willing to put his best efforts and get in to the depth of the subject to understand it better.

His association with us was very fruitful and we wish him all the best in his future endeavors.

Sincerely,

Nizamuddin Zafar

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